

TABLE 2. Main isolated or uncultured genera, their read % found in Brazilian leafcutters, and their close relatives already described as symbiotic with leafcutters from the Republic of Panama (RP) or Texas (USA).

Detection	Genus	Read %				Id (%)	Related strain	Location	Ref.
		S ⁺	L	R	C				
16S rDNA library	<i>Liberibacter</i> ⁿ	1.25	89.05	6.14	4.6	95.55			
	<i>Terasakiella</i> ⁿ	0.04	0.44	30.21	44.10	98.86	RhiAcro1	RP	1
	<i>Bartonella</i> ⁿ	85.36	0.13	5.13	0.09	99.09			
	<i>Mesoplasma</i>	0	0	44.41	38.23	98.47/98.9	OTU-1544	USA	2
	<i>Entomoplasma</i>	0	0	4.49	4.17	99.57/99.78	EntAcro1	RP	1
Cultivation + 16S rDNA library	<i>Entomoplasma</i>	0	0	4.49	4.17	91.42/91.85	EntAcro2	RP	
	<i>Methylobacterium</i> ^N	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	96-99	<i>Methylobacterium</i>	Brazil	3
	<i>Ralstonia</i> ^N	0.0005	0.0005	0.0005	0.0005	96-99	165 B08NCY14_206		
	<i>Acinetobacter</i>	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	99	984 T05BL07Y10-167		
	<i>Pseudomonas</i> ^N	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	96	1262 A10FBY14 124	USA	2
<i>Brachybacterium</i>	0.008	0.008	0.008	0.008	99	57 P13NE01Y14 497			
					92	1510 T03BL02Y10 4861			
					94	942 P31NE08Y14 390394			

⁺S: *Atta sexdens*; L: *Atta laevigata*; R: *Acromyrmex rugosus*; C: *Acromyrmex coronatus*

1: Sapountzis et al., 2015; 2 Meirelles et al., 2016; 3 Martinez et al., 2019.

^NNitrogen-fixing; ⁿputative nitrogen fixing or recycling.